

MODERN METHODS OF QUALITY CONTROL AND SAFETY OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

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Annotation: In this formulation, the main features of quality control and safety of food products are moxokama, carried out only on the basis of the use of modern methods of analysis, mainly in methods of physical chemical analysis.

Key words: Quality control, food safety, physical chemistry methods of analysis, work skills, assimilation, dissimilation, energy.

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the quality and safety of food is an important task facing not only food industry workers. How a person eats and what he eats today depends on his health, efficiency and efficiency, that is, the return on his work and personal contribution, the quality of his life, as well as the life of his children, that is, future generations.

The quality of food includes the following aspects

1. Food quality related to physical and chemical indicators and safety indicators. This aspect implies the implementation of quality control of food products for compliance with the requirements of regulatory documentation for the content of heavy metals, radionuclides, pesticides, other chemical pollutants, pathogenic microorganisms, protozoa, helminths and biological toxins that pose a danger to human health [1,2].

2. The nutritional value of the product depends primarily on the content of digestible substances and elements in an optimal ratio and is determined not only by the content of proteins, fats and carbohydrates, macro- and microelements, vitamins, but also by the amino acid composition of proteins, fatty acid composition of lipids, composition of organic acids, etc. [1-3]

Solving the problem of authenticity and identity requires appropriate methods for identifying chemicals that are part of food [1].

Quality control, safety and nutritional value of food is also very important. Currently, levels of adequate need - "recommended consumption rates" – have been developed for the main food substances (proteins, fats and carbohydrates), as well as for several dozen micronutrients (vitamins, a number of macro- and microelements, polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), flavonoids, etc.) [1-14]. To adequately determine the content of food and biologically active substances in food, a broad technological and methodological base is needed.

METHODS AND RESULTS

The following research methods are most widely used.

1. Spectral research methods – a set of methods for qualitative and quantitative determination of the composition of an object based on the study of the spectra of the interaction of matter with radiation, including the spectra of electromagnetic radiation, acoustic waves, mass and energy distributions of elementary particles, etc. They allow you to get the most complete information about the most important properties of the product. Spectral analysis is used to determine pectin substances, phenolic compounds, macro- and microelements, the content of heavy metals, the degree of oxidation of fats, etc.[2,3].

2. Chromatographic research methods are indispensable in assessing the quality and safety of food products with a very complex chemical composition. Chromatography is a process based on the repeated repetition of the sorption and desorption of a substance when it is moved in the flow of a mobile phase along a stationary sorbent. The separation of complex mixtures by chromatographic method is based on the different sorption properties of the mixture components.

For example, gas-liquid chromatography (GC) is the most important method for studying the composition of fatty acids of natural oils and fats, as well as lipids isolated from various foods. In addition, GZHC is used in determining the content of fat-soluble vitamins, synthetic dyes, preservatives, amino acids, carbohydrates, food aromatics, pesticides, and others [2,3].

3. Methods of capillary electrophoresis analysis of complex mixtures are based on the use of electrokinetic phenomena – electromigration of ions and other charged particles and electroosmosis – for separation and determination of components. The capillary electrophoresis method makes it possible to determine the amino acid composition of food proteins, the composition of organic acids, the content of fructose, glucose, sucrose, etc.

CONCLUSION

The use of modern research methods makes it possible to solve the problems of quality control and food safety, therefore, the health and life expectancy of the population.

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